

Motivation and Competences in Writing Action Researches: Basis for Teachers' Coaching and Training Program

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ABSTRACT

Capacitating teachers doing action researches provides an avenue to innovate teaching practices in the classroom that will give a greater impact to the total development of the students in public schools. This study assessed the level of academic writing motivation of the teachers and how it influences their competence in doing action researches. Descriptive and Correlational research design was used to achieve the objectives of the study participated by 46 public elementary school teachers in Sto. Angel District of DepEd-San Pablo City. It was found out that the teachers are motivated in doing academic writing outputs to properly document the best practices they have imposed in teaching and learning processes with an average level of research competence. Also, their average level of academic writing motivation has a moderate significant relationship to the competence level of the teachers in writing action researches. This further show that teachers should be given training program in conducting action researches highlighting the technical aspects, methodology, writing analysis and interpretation and proper citation enough to become equipped in documenting their teaching initiatives.

Keywords: *Writing Motivation, Research Competence, Elementary Teachers*

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INTRODUCTION

The Department of Education is on its progress in developing the research capacity of its educators to maximize the research output to address the needs of their clientele. They encourage teachers to work on Action Researches which would bring out best practices of the teachers to deliver quality teaching and learning processes [1, 2]. Simple and strategic ways of pedagogical practices will be employed by the teachers and test its effectiveness to ensure that learners will be able to cope up with the real score of learning the lessons [3, 4]. Teachers as well will learn the research skills which is important for them to scientifically innovate several teaching applications. By the conduct of action researches, teachers will be able to reflect on their teaching elements, identify potential classroom conflicts and employ actions to effectively serve their student-clientele [5, 6].

In DepEd CALABARZON [7], their regional office annually calls for paper nationwide and spearhead a conference for Basic Education Researchers for them to present their research output that is aligned to their BERA towards the conceptualization of the conference themes on evidence-based actions for ensuring access to a complete basic education, improving the quality of education and ensuring effective, transparent and engaging governance. The regional level is active to ensure that teachers will engage themselves in doing action researches which evident to their participation to international conferences organized by the region office. The Department of Education in region IV-A CALABARZON also provides financial assistance to teachers who work on action research through their Basic Education Research Fund.

When it comes to newly hired teachers who just entered the teaching force, they find it challenging to critically employ learning activities and practices in the educational premise. In an undeniably challenging and novel work of the teachers, as indicated by Hine [8], the requirement for instructors, academic heads, and educational policies to become engaged with different professional mentoring and coaching is evident. Doing action researchers and mentoring teachers to do so gives those teachers working in the training framework with a deliberate, intelligent way to deal with skills enhancement and study areas that needs improvement [9, 10].

Teacher's motivation in writing academic works was known as a significant factor that influences the performance of the students in the mastery of different learning competencies [11]. The writing motivation itself comprises domains including self-adequacy, convictions, perspectives, and objective direction. The inspiration, motivation and inward convictions should be developed among the writers to exhibit full potential of writing. Teachers who believe in their capacity to write can exhibit more prominent assurance in trying to compose amazingly well. Endeavours to foster

writing proficiency among teachers won't have a huge effect except if they cultivate the to work on creative write-ups [12].

The motivation in writing researches might be significantly more prominent or more vulnerable than one's inspiration to talk or read which is probably going to change across differed execution settings [13]. It is noted that positive motivation is related with vital conduct, task tirelessness, and scholastic accomplishment in writing. Along these lines, teachers who are persuaded send learning and adapting procedures (e.g., appropriated intermittent survey of material, outline of key ideas and thoughts, self-consolation, looking for help) to expand their instructive potential, work through difficulties and misfortune without surrendering, and perform better in school. Four expansive parts of accomplishment, as teachers are motivated to write, have been distinguished by analysts: self-viability convictions, objective directions, individual and situational interest, and attributions for results [14].

One of the major professional preparing destinations among the teachers in writing educational papers is the premise and experience improvement of proficiencies in action research at the examination level. Status to lead logical exploration make up piece of this turn of events, just like the abilities of writing researches, dominating useful techniques, tools and methods and advances in the particular level controlled by the preparation, and the capacity to work in proficient circumstances of vulnerability [15].

During school accreditations and standards checking of supervisors and division level audit, research output is one of the parameters being checked. Likewise, when it comes to school based management and school ranking to national levels, research is one of the key indicators being assessed. This is an indication that teachers should be trained and be skilled in doing researches to contribute to the status of school performances. There sets of competencies that teachers have to obtain in order to be become skilled in doing research. Researcher skills can be acquired and be developed whenever they attend seminars, trainings, mentoring programs, coaching with colleagues or attending higher level of educational venues. It is also noted in some studies that when teachers have experience doing it, acquisition of the skills can also be manifested. [16].

Teachers have to be more knowledgeable and be more skilled in doing research for them to innovate teaching practices that fit the learning situation of their students. Though there are some research claims showing interests of the teachers in analyzing only their roles in the educative progress of the students and not in the competencies set that they need to obtain in order to effectively plan their instruction. The skills of the teachers were carefully studied regarding development plans in training, advancement of educator schooling, logical after-effects of instructive methodologies in different fields [17].

The role of teachers in school is one of the most important resources for school effectiveness. Capacitating teacher's skills in different aspects may help them to grow personally and professionally. The findings of this study were analyzed that might be worthwhile for the Department of Education, to pay more attention and to make an effort of promoting research involvements in planning different programs to enhance teachers' capability in writing action researches. This led to the activity proposed by the school heads of Sto. Angel district in collaboration with the Laguna State Polytechnic University-San Pablo City Campus through the research ability coaching and training for the elementary school teachers that will help them a lot to learn the research competency for free.

This study determine the academic writing motivation and research competence of public elementary and secondary school teachers that is an initial step to the soon to propose extension program to be conducted by Laguna State Polytechnic University-College of Teacher Education to public elementary and secondary school teachers in San Pablo City.

Specifically this study was administered to:

- 1) determine the level of motivation of the elementary teachers in Sto Angel District in writing academic studies.
- 2) assess the research competence of the elementary teachers in terms of: technical aspect; writing introduction; methods; results and discussions; referencing; other research related competence.
- 3) Find-out whether there is a significant relationship between the academic writing motivation of the elementary teachers and their research competence.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research project utilized descriptive and co relational research designs to assess the academic writing motivation and research capabilities which was the initial step in crafting the plan of the soon to propose extension service of Laguna State Polytechnic University- College of Teacher Education. The participants of the study were the 45randomly sampled elementary school teachers of Sto Angel District in San Pablo City, during the academic year 2019-

2020. The questionnaires used in the study were adapted from the work of Payne [18] as to the instrument in assessing the academic writing motivation and from Gómez & Panaligan [16] assessing the level of research competencies and satisfaction of the faculty members.

The researcher was invited in the school locale to deliver a training to the teachers, he asked the school principals in the district for the permission to assess first how motivated the teachers are in doing action researches and their capability of writing. As a result, the data were tabulated and presented in the paper that led the proponent to work on an extension program for the teachers in the school district. This would benefit them to increase the number of committed teachers who will work in action researches. All the data revealed in the study were treated with strict confidentiality and anonymity of the participants. This only serves as a scholarly output for the Laguna State Polytechnic University-College of Teacher education to plan effectively potential extension program for elementary school teachers.

DISCUSSION

The Academic writing motivation of the elementary school teachers in District of Sto. Angel was assessed first to determine if they have the drive to write scholarly articles to properly document their best practices in the classroom through action research to be conducted.

Table 1. Level of Academic Writing Motivation

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Enjoyment to work on scholarly tasks.	3.46	0.86	Moderate
2. Interests in writing academic output.	3.12	0.78	Moderate
3. Consciousness on technical matter in writing.	2.98	0.71	Moderate
4. Participate in online and offline written discussions.	3.05	0.97	Moderate
5. Expressive in writing personal ideas.	3.38	0.80	Moderate
6. Writing for future directions.	3.21	0.72	Moderate
Overall	3.20	0.81	Moderate

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Very High, 3.50-4.49 High, 2.50-3.49 Moderate, 1.50-2.49 Low, 1.00-1.49 Poor

As described in Table 1, the teachers in Sto. Angel District of San Pablo City are moderately motivated in writing scholarly works. This shows that they have average level of academic writing motivation. Teachers are motivated to write and that they wanted to learn working with action researches. Becoming a better writer is important to the elementary teachers that they are worried if the one's to be constructed will still hold the power of their profession as to what is expected to them. This only means that the reason behind average level of writing motivation as to scholarly work is attributed to what Boscolo & Hidi [19] described that the writing tasks considered by teachers are often multifaceted, challenging, and supposed as risky, therefore, the motivation in writing lends the situation to be examined on teacher's views of his or her capacity in writing good statements. This implies that there is a need to boost the motivational level of the teachers for them to construct effectively writing scholarly works.

As observed in the table, elementary teachers who participated in the study enjoyed working with action researches for they understood the benefits it could bring for them and their students as well. They know that through action researches, they will be able to identify different pedagogical innovative ways to make their classroom transformed to an exciting one [20, 21]. Working with action researches as well helps teachers be more expressive. They can share and reflect on their teaching practices which elevates their personal ideas in teaching to standards and innovations they may developed. Teachers reflection of the educative processes will be practiced in order to carefully plan the success of the instructive processes [22, 23].

Aside with the academic writing motivation level of respondents of the study, it is also important to assess the competence of the teachers in writing researches. This will be a guide for the researchers to prepare a plan of activities to be provided to them which will make them prepared in the training and coaching program. The research competence of the teachers was assessed as to the technical aspect, competence in writing introduction, determining appropriate methodology, providing results and discussions, generating conclusions and recommendations, summarizing references and other aspect of writing researches.

Table 2. Level of Research Competence of the Elementary Teachers

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Technical Aspect	3.00	0.62	Moderate
2. Writing Introduction	2.93	0.80	Moderate
3. Research Methodology	2.84	0.80	Moderate
4. Presenting Results and Discussion	2.79	0.79	Moderate

5. Delivering Conclusions and Recommendations	2.78	0.76	Moderate
6. Referencing	2.91	0.81	Moderate
7. Other Parts of the Research	3.01	0.69	Moderate
Overall	2.89	0.75	Moderate

As shown in table 2, the elementary teachers covered in the study are moderately competent in terms of the technical aspect of writing researches. What they least considered is the research paper format which denotes a little knowledge on the construct and sequence of contents in preparing the documented forms of action researches. Even though grammar and sentence construction obtained highest mean it still denotes that the teachers have an average level of competence in their ability of processing their grammar and constructing well their sentences [24].

The table also indicates the competence of the teachers in writing the introduction. Writing the introduction requires the rationale for undertaking the study and clearly describes the main purpose of conducting it [25]. It is also where the foundation of the research problem the researcher would like to explore. However, the respondents of the study are moderately competent in constructing a good introduction for the study. This means that they still need guidance in doing so. This should be carefully discussed in a training program to be given to them [26].

The level of research competence of the teachers as to the appropriate methodology to be considered in making researches is also indicated in the table. As revealed, the respondents are moderately competent in all aspect of methodology. It is evident that they moderately knowledgeable of different research methodology that can be applied in their research concepts. Even though they assessed data entry or encoding as highest indicator they were found with moderate competence in doing it. The least assessed is the application of treatment via statistical tools appropriate to the statement of the problem set in the study, with this, the trainer would like to share with them the knowledge of using the basics of SPSS, SSB and data analysis of Microsoft Excel [27].

As revealed by table 5, the respondents of the study are moderately competent in giving the results and discussion of the study. This means that they know how to present, interpret and give correlated literature but with background knowledge on it. The presentation that mostly utilized by teachers in elementary whenever they work on researches are graphs and tables. The graphs are widely used in the presentation of respondents' profile while tables are used to present the descriptive analysis of the researchers based on their posted objectives of the study [28, 29]. This means that these areas will still be part of the training and coaching program to be given to them.

As to the level of competence of the respondents in making conclusions and recommendations, they least assessed their capacity of synthesizing the result and with same moderate competence in expressing additional value and formulation of appropriate recommendations. This imply that respondents have little knowledge of the competency that requires more training to become competent.

The respondents were found to be moderately competent in making a summary of their reference list. They rated higher their ability to access available and updated materials for they know where to get related literature using the web sources. However, moderate competence means an average knowledge that still needs more training acquainting them with the use of search engines and tools that can help them achieve good presentation of references following the standards of APA.

Table 3. Correlation between Motivation in Writing and Research Competence

Research Competence	Academic Writing Motivation		
	r	Sig.	Interpretation
1. Technical Aspect	.512**	0.000	Significant
2. Writing Introduction	.435**	0.002	Significant
3. Research Methodology	.386**	0.007	Significant
4. Presenting Results and Discussion	.387**	0.007	Significant
5. Delivering Conclusions and Recommendations	.418**	0.003	Significant
6. Referencing	.425**	0.003	Significant
7. Other Parts of the Research	.493**	0.000	Significant

It is shown in the table that there is significant relationship between the academic writing motivation of the teachers and their competence level in all of the variables considered. The relationship shows positive moderate relationship which implies that whenever the researcher is are motivated in doing research task this provides avenue for them to perform better in accomplishing it with greater level of competence.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The elementary teachers participated in the study have moderate academic writing motivation. Becoming a better writer is important to them. Elementary teachers are moderately competent in writing researches considering the technical aspect, writing introduction, determining appropriate methodology, providing results and discussions, generating conclusions and recommendations, summarizing references and other aspect of writing researches. There is a positive significant relationship between the academic writing motivation and the level of competence in writing researches. This implies that the higher academic writing motivation will drive an individual to be more competent in writing researches.

There is a need to boost the motivation of the teachers in writing researches. This could be done through a seminar that will make them realize the worth of doing research and how their research outputs will be credited to their personal and professional developments. Conduct of training and coaching program is advised to be comprehensively done by the school in collaboration with research experts in the field or in higher education to highlight the potential of the teachers in writing researches concerning the general format of doing research through IMRAD. Increase the motivation of the teachers in writing or documenting their best practices in the classroom through the conduct of action researches for this can make them better professionals equipped with research skills.

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